

Influence of azolla, sesbania, and urea supergranule (USG) on rice yield and nitrogen uptake

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We evaluated the effect of N-fixing azolla and sesbania on yield and N uptake of IR50 rice in field experiments 1987 dry season and 1987-88 wet season (Co 43).

Azolla microphylla, *A. filiculoides*, *Sesbania rostrata*, and *S. aculeata* were incorporated at 2 kg/m² with and without N. The N content of the bio-fertilizers was estimated on dry weight basis as 2.45% in *A. microphylla*, 2.68% in *A. filiculoides*, 3.92% in *S. rostrata*, and 3.25% in *S. aculeata* during the dry season and 3.08, 2.96, 3.68, and 3.07% during the wet season. N as USG was basal, applied at 100 kg/ha. Prilled urea and unfertilized controls were also maintained.

In both seasons, grain yield was significantly higher with *S. rostrata* + USG, *S. aculeata* + USG, and *A. filiculoides* + USG (see table). In the dry season, *S. rostrata* without USG yielded significantly higher than USG (100 kg/ha) alone. Straw yields followed similar trends.

N uptake in grain and straw in the dry season was significantly higher with *S. rostrata* + USG. Trends in the wet seasons were similar.

In general, incorporation of N-fixing green manure in combination with USG increased the yield and N uptake. □

Influence on rice yield and N uptake of azolla and sesbania incorporation with and without USG application. Tamil Nadu, India, 1987-88.

Treatment	1987 dry season (IR50)				1987-88 wet season (CO 43)			
	Yield (t/ha)		N uptake (kg/ha)		Yield (t/ha)		N uptake (kg/ha)	
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw
Untreated	3.7	6.6	28.4	26.3	4.4	7.1	34.8	29.5
Prilled urea	4.6	9.0	41.2	40.5	5.7	8.3	48.5	41.7
USG	5.1	11.0	48.8	62.5	6.0	8.8	55.1	45.9
<i>Azolla microphylla</i>	4.5	7.3	39.4	34.0	5.3	9.5	41.4	44.1
<i>Azolla filiculoides</i>	4.5	8.1	40.7	36.0	5.4	10.1	43.6	47.7
<i>Sesbania rostrata</i>	5.6	10.7	51.4	52.6	5.3	10.2	43.6	50.6
<i>Sesbania aculeata</i>	5.2	10.7	47.6	48.5	5.3	9.6	42.9	45.5
USG + <i>A. microphylla</i>	6.0	12.4	60.5	70.3	6.3	11.2	58.0	58.9
USG + <i>A. filiculoides</i>	6.3	12.6	61.1	70.5	6.7	12.1	60.7	61.8
USG + <i>S. rostrata</i>	6.6	14.3	70.2	86.2	7.1	12.3	67.7	69.5
USG + <i>S. aculeata</i>	6.3	13.5	61.4	77.9	6.9	11.9	63.4	65.2
SE	0.1	0.3	2.2	5.2	0.2	0.5	3.0	4.9
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.3	0.6	4.7	10.8	0.4	1.0	6.3	10.1

Effect on rice yield of biofertilizers plus inorganic fertilizer

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We evaluated rice yields with sesbania, barnyard manure (BM), and azolla biofertilizer in combination with inorganic fertilizer during 1988 wet season. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications. Soil was sandy clay loam with pH 8.0, 0.056% total N, 13 kg available P/ha, and 332 kg K/ha.

Fresh azolla (12.5 t/ha) was incorporated by treading in no standing water 1-5 d after transplanting GR11. *Sesbania aculeata* was grown in situ, coarsely chopped, and incorporated before transplanting. BM was incorporated before transplanting. P was

applied at 50 kg/ha before trans-planting.

Urea supergranule (USG) alone, prilled urea (PU) + sesbania, and 100 kg N/ha as ammonium sulfate gave sig-

nificantly higher yields than PU, PU + azolla, and PU + BM (see table).

USG alone also gave significantly higher N uptake (105 kg/ha) than all treatments. □

Influence of N source on rice grain yield and nutrient uptake. Nawagam, India, 1988 wet season.

Nitrogen treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Nutrient uptake (kg/ha)		
			N	P	K
No fertilizer N	3.4	3.5	50.60	7.12	64.31
100 kg N/ha					
USG point placed at 10-12 cm soil depth	5.8	7.0	105.05	13.04	136.51
PU 2/3 basal + 1/3 5-7 d before panicle initiation (DBPI)	5.0	4.8	68.32	9.83	85.79
Azolla 3/6 N + PU (1/6 basal + 2/6 5-7 DBPI)	4.9	4.2	70.94	9.43	92.24
Sesbania 3/6 N + PU (1/6 basal + 2/6 5-7 DBPI)	5.3	5.0	83.63	10.22	123.08
BM 3/6 N + PU (1/6 basal + 2/6 5-7 DBPI)	4.5	4.1	67.65	7.77	83.86
PU 1/4 basal + 1/2 at max tillering + 1/4 at booting	4.8	5.9	80.27	9.52	105.68
Ammonium sulfate 1/4 basal + 1/2 at max tillering + 1/4 at booting	5.7	6.0	92.24	10.94	131.48
LSD (0.05)	0.6	0.8	7.86	1.27	14.47